

EU Taxonomy Activity for Eutrophic Water Remediation

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PROPOSAL September 15, 2025

The proposed new activity addresses **remediation of eutrophic water bodies (freshwater and coastal/marine)** with the aim of reducing methane (CH₄) emissions while restoring ecosystem functions of oxygen balance and nutrient cycling..

Detailed scientific and policy review for climate mitigation and green finance is provided in Markelova & Chuprina (2025)¹.

Environmental objective: Climate Change Mitigation (Article 9(a) of Regulation (EU) 2020/852).

Level	Reference	Content
Activity title	New activity	Remediation of eutrophic water bodies
Description of the activity	—	Initiation, development and realisation of in-situ measures primarily aimed at reducing methane (CH ₄) emissions from eutrophic waters, while restoring ecosystem functions of oxygen balance and nutrient cycling. Includes natural and artificial aquatic ecosystems such as lakes, reservoirs, rivers, ponds, coastal/marine waters, urban ponds, irrigation ponds, and stormwater basins.
Substantial contribution to climate change mitigation	SC-1	Primary metric (preferred): Verified reduction in methane (CH ₄) flux versus baseline, aggregated over the reporting year. Projects shall demonstrate a statistically robust downward change (with quantified uncertainty) and may use 30% reduction over a 10-year assessment period calibrated to site conditions and quantified uncertainty. Where Tier-1 flux monitoring is not yet feasible: projects follow the proxy pathway (chlorophyll-a reduction by ~30%; hypolimnetic DO

¹ Markelova, E., & Chuprina, E. (2025). Remediation of eutrophic water bodies: A nature-based solution for climate mitigation and green finance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17128109>

		$\geq \sim 4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) with a time-bound plan to upgrade to direct CH ₄ flux monitoring.
	SC-2	Eligible measures: phosphorus inactivation, aeration/oxygenation, sediment capping/dredging, biomass harvesting, biomanipulation, optional bio-dispersants with SDS. Exclusions: ex-situ conservation, hazardous pollutant remediation, offsets.
	SC-3	Co-metrics (reporting): dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a, cyanotoxins, global warming potential.
	SC-4	Monitoring, reporting & verification: tiered MRV system (direct flux, proxy indicators, narrative evidence); independent verification at commissioning and every 10 years.
Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)	—	Criteria under Appendices A–D: adaptation risk screening (A); WFD/MSFD alignment, UWWTD recast for external loads (B); chemical and sediment safeguards (C); biodiversity safeguards, no IAS, EIA only where legally required (D).
Minimum safeguards	Article 18 of Regulation (EU) 2020/852	Compliance with OECD Guidelines, UNGPs, ILO core conventions; equitable public access to water bodies maintained.
Additional specifications	—	Scope includes natural and artificial freshwater and coastal systems; exclusions include contaminated site clean-up and biodiversity offsets; operational energy use accounted for in GHG balance; nutrient-load reduction as enabling measure; optional reference to IUCN NbS Standard.
Indicative NACE codes	—	F43.99 (specialised construction); E36.00 (water supply, when relevant); M72.19 (research/pilot projects).
Indicative CEPA class	—	Class 6: Protection of biodiversity and landscapes / water protection (Regulation (EU) No 691/2011).

ANNEX

Technical screening criteria for determining the conditions under which an economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to the remediation of eutrophic water bodies and for determining whether that economic activity causes no significant harm to any of the other environmental objectives

Activity title

(Short): Remediation of eutrophic water bodies.

(Extended): Remediation of eutrophic water bodies to reduce methane (CH₄) emissions and restore ecosystem conditions.

Description of the activity

Initiation, development and realisation on own account or on a fee or contract basis, of in-situ remediation measures aimed primarily at reducing methane (CH₄) emissions² from eutrophic water bodies³ and restoring ecosystem function by stabilising oxygen and nutrient cycles. The activity covers all types of aquatic ecosystems affected by eutrophication⁴, encompassing both natural and artificial systems⁵. It applies to freshwater bodies such as lakes, reservoirs, rivers, and ponds, as well as to coastal and marine areas prone to algal blooms and hypoxia. Artificial ecosystems, including urban ponds, stormwater retention lakes, irrigation ponds, and other man-made basins, are explicitly included where they are subject to eutrophication and methane emissions.

The economic activity includes:

- (a) activities of in-situ⁶ remediation, consisting of interventions directly applied within the aquatic environment to suppress methane production and improve oxygen and nutrient dynamics; such measures include phosphorus inactivation, aeration/oxygenation, sediment capping or

² ‘Methane emissions’ from water bodies include both diffusive and ebullitive fluxes, in accordance with IPCC 2019 Refinement to the 2006 Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories.

³ ‘Water body means a distinct and significant volume of water, whether surface freshwater or marine coastal waters, as defined under Directive 2000/60/EC (Water Framework Directive), Article 2, points (10)–(12). For the purpose of this activity, the term also includes artificial water bodies such as reservoirs, urban ponds, stormwater retention basins, and other man-made basins where eutrophication processes result in greenhouse gas emissions.

⁴ ‘Eutrophication’ means the enrichment of water by nutrients, especially compounds of nitrogen and/or phosphorus, causing an accelerated growth of algae and higher forms of plant life, as defined in Directive 91/271/EEC, Annex I.

⁵ The IPCC 2019 Refinement recognizes “other constructed waterbodies” (including farm ponds, aquaculture ponds, canals, and ditches) as a source of CH₄ and CO₂ emissions that may be included in national greenhouse gas inventories. Nations are encouraged to account for methane emissions from small constructed ponds (e.g. < 8 ha) as part of “Other Constructed Waterbodies” under Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry, although empirical data and emission factors are presently limited. (Malerba et al., 2024; IPCC, 2019).

⁶ ‘In-situ conservation’ means the conservation of ecosystems and natural habitats and the maintenance and recovery of viable populations of species in their natural surroundings.

targeted dredging, biomass harvesting, biomanipulation, and application of bio-dispersants to reduce algal biofilms;

(b) activities of restoration, defined as actions actively or passively assisting the recovery of eutrophic ecosystems towards or to a stable condition, including through the reduction of algal biomass and re-establishment of balanced nutrient and oxygen cycles.

The economic activity does not include:

(a) ex-situ⁷ conservation actions in the sense of the Convention on Biological Diversity (e.g., aquaria, seed banks, zoological collections), which do not involve emission reductions from water bodies;

(b) hazardous pollutant remediation⁸ (heavy metals, hydrocarbons, etc.), which is covered under separate Taxonomy activities;

(c) catchment-level nutrient load reduction⁹ (wastewater treatment, agricultural nutrient control), which are enabling but fall under other Taxonomy categories.

The economic activities in this category are partially covered under NACE codes E36.00, F43.99, and M72.19as referred to in the statistical classification of economic activities established by Regulation (EC) No 1893/2006. The activities relate to Class 6 of the statistical classification of environmental protection activities (CEPA) established by Regulation (EU) No 691/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

Technical screening criteria

Substantial contribution to Climate Change Mitigation

1. General conditions

1.1. The activity contributes to climate change mitigation by directly reducing greenhouse gas emissions from eutrophic aquatic ecosystems, including freshwater and coastal/marine waters, through the restoration of balanced nutrient and oxygen cycles.

1.2. The activity's primary climate outcome is reduction of methane (CH₄) emissions. Where operators choose to report total CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) outcomes, they shall use IPCC AR6¹⁰ values and state the

⁷ 'Ex-situ conservation' means the conservation of components of biological diversity outside their natural habitats, as per Article 2 of the Convention on Biological Diversity.

⁸ Activities primarily targeting hazardous pollutants are addressed under other technical screening criteria in Annex I as amended by Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2485.

⁹ External load-reduction measures are covered under separate activities and must align with Directive (EU) 2024/3019 on urban waste water treatment and Directive 91/676/EEC (Nitrates Directive).

¹⁰ CO₂-equivalent values are calculated using Global Warming Potentials (GWP) for non-fossil (biogenic) methane from the IPCC AR6, baseline case without land-carbon feedbacks: GWP-100 = 27.9 and GWP-20 = 81.2 (IPCC AR6).

time horizon and feedback variant consistently. Where oxygenation or mixing converts CH₄ to CO₂¹¹, the net CO₂e effect shall be transparently reported.

1.3. The activity may be carried out by any type of operator irrespective of the main domain of activity.

2. Initial description of the area

2.1. The activity is based on a detailed description of the ecological conditions of the water body, which contains at least the following elements:

- (a) mapping of the water body, including depth, stratification regime, and extent of eutrophic areas;
- (b) identification of nutrient sources (external vs. internal loading), historical legacy of nutrient and contaminant accumulation, and key drivers of methane emissions;
- (c) baseline measurements of methane (CH₄) fluxes (primary KPI) and, where feasible, CO₂ and N₂O, as well as proxy indicators (dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a, and/or cyanotoxin frequency¹²);
- (d) assessment of climate risks such as heatwaves, stratification lengthening, or altered hydrology;
- (e) the potential for improvement, including connectivity to upstream/downstream systems.

3. Management plan or equivalent instrument

3.1. The remediation activity is covered by a management plan or by an equivalent instrument, such as a restoration plan, which is regularly updated and, in any case, at least every ten years, and contains the following information:

- (a) a description of the expected contribution to climate change mitigation primarily through CH₄ emissions reduction, and to water-quality recovery, considering the relevant policy context;
- (b) the list of targeted ecosystems and indicators, including CH₄ fluxes (primary KPI) and, where feasible, CO₂/N₂O, and proxy indicators (dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a, cyanotoxins);
- (c) the duration of the plan and a clear description of the remediation objectives for each water body or water body segment, and of the corresponding measures that address identified pressures and threats (external and internal nutrient loads, stratification, algal blooms, legacy sediment contamination). The plan specifies deadlines for achieving the objectives. Where these exceed the plan's duration, intermediate progress (milestones) is defined;

¹¹ AR6 acknowledges GWP-based reporting; CO₂ has far lower GWP than CH₄.

¹² 'Cyanotoxins' include microcystins, cylindrospermopsin and other toxins produced by cyanobacteria; see WHO background documents for drinking-water and recreational water guidelines.

- (d) a description of the threats and pressures that could hinder the achievement of the remediation objectives, including projected effects of climate change such as higher temperatures, prolonged stratification, and altered hydrology;
- (e) the measures to ensure that all DNSH criteria for this activity are achieved, including safeguards against harmful chemical inputs, ecotoxic effects, or damage to connected ecosystems;
- (f) consideration of societal issues, including consultation of stakeholders (municipalities, water authorities, communities, NGOs), preservation of recreational and cultural uses, and co-benefits such as safer water supply and phosphorus recovery;
- (g) where applicable, a description of enhanced ecosystem services resulting from remediation, such as greenhouse gas reduction, biodiversity recovery, safe water supply, phosphorus recovery, recreation opportunities, and resilience against climate risks;
- (h) a monitoring scheme aligned with MRV priorities, including corrective measures;
- (i) the persons and organisations involved in implementing the remediation, and where relevant, collaborations or partnerships with research institutions, verification bodies, and private operators to achieve the objectives;
- (j) the measures taken to ensure transparency about the remediation objectives, measures, monitoring results, and independent verification;
- (k) the funding necessary for implementing the measures, for monitoring and verification, and for periodic audits. Given that many local communities cannot pre-finance interventions, the plan shall explicitly identify access to green bonds, sustainability-linked loans, or public–private blended finance as required.

3.2. Where the management plan or equivalent instrument does not contain all the elements specified in point 3.1, the missing information is provided by the operator of the activity.

3.3. Phased implementation and working areas:

3.3.1. The remediation activity may be implemented in phases across clearly delineated working areas (management units) within a water body, rather than requiring full-scale implementation at project start. Working areas are defined using ecological and operational criteria (e.g. bathymetry/stratification, proximity to inflows, legacy sediment hotspots, access and safety).

3.3.2. Each working area shall have: (a) mapped boundaries; (b) a baseline (including, as applicable, CO₂/CH₄/N₂O fluxes and/or proxy indicators); (c) measures selected; (d) objectives/milestones and timelines; and (e) an MRV design aligned to MRV Evidence Tiers 1–3.

3.3.3. Eligibility under SC-1 may be assessed and claimed at the working-area level using the Outcome Pathways A–C, with Pathway A (CH₄ outcome) as the preferred route. Activity-level results are then compiled from working-area outcomes. Where a flux baseline exists by area, aggregation uses baseline-emission weighting; where it does not, surface-area weighting (or another justified metric) may be applied and disclosed.

3.3.4. The management plan shall set a phasing sequence (order of working areas), triggers for expansion (e.g. achievement of defined DO/chlorophyll thresholds or verification of CO₂e reduction), and interim risk controls to avoid spatial leakage (e.g. exporting blooms/hypoxia to untreated zones).

3.3.5. Audits under §8 may be scheduled per phase/working area to reduce costs, provided the auditor can verify both unit-level outcomes and the aggregate activity performance.

3.3.6. Where remote sensing is used, it should cover both treated and untreated areas to document spatial representativeness, with periodic in-situ ground-truthing per §7.1.

3.3.7. Partial implementation is acceptable, provided the plan includes a time-bound pathway to address remaining material emission sources within the water body or a reasoned justification (technical, ecological, permitting) for deferring specific areas.

4. Performance thresholds (SC-1)

4.1. Projects demonstrate substantial contribution by achieving improvements consistent with one of the following indicative pathways, with the exact timeframe and magnitude adjusted to the scale and conditions of each individual project.

SC-1.0 Scope of accounting. Eligibility is primarily assessed on reduction of methane (CH₄) flux relative to a documented baseline. Operators may additionally report total CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) outcomes using IPCC AR6 values, stating the time horizon and feedback variant. Where oxygenation causes CH₄ oxidation to CO₂, the net CO₂e effect shall be explained if CO₂e is reported.

SC-1.1 Outcome pathways (choose one). Projects demonstrate substantial contribution by meeting one of the following Outcome Pathways, with timeframes and magnitudes calibrated to site conditions:

Pathway A — Direct GHG outcome (preferred): Verified reduction in methane (CH₄) flux relative to baseline, aggregated over reporting years. An indicative, non-binding ambition benchmark of ~30% reduction over a 10-year assessment period may be used, calibrated to site conditions and quantified uncertainty; it is not a pass/fail criterion. (Projects may additionally disclose total CO₂e where feasible.)

Pathway B — Proxy outcome: Sustained downward trend in chlorophyll-a and recovery of hypolimnetic DO during summer stratification over a 10-year assessment period. Indicative, non-binding ambition benchmarks are ~30% chlorophyll-a reduction and DO typically \geq ~4 mg·L⁻¹; these are guidance targets, not thresholds. Projects on Pathway B commit to assessing feasibility of Tier-1 direct CH₄ flux monitoring for the next verification cycle.

Pathway C — Transitional outcome (narrative): Documented external nutrient-load reductions, suppression of algal blooms, and oxygen recovery where higher-level monitoring is temporarily infeasible; includes a plan and timeline to upgrade to Tier-2 or Tier-1 evidence.

SC-1.2 Net-benefit check. Operational energy use (aeration, pumping, mixing) is reported. Where CO₂e outcomes are reported, operational emissions are included in the CO₂e balance.

5. Eligible measures (SC-2)

5.1. Eligible in-situ measures include, as appropriate to site diagnostics:

- (a) phosphorus inactivation (e.g., using mineral binding agents);
- (b) aeration or oxygenation;
- (c) sediment management (e.g. capping, targeted dredging for eutrophic biomass);
- (d) biomass harvesting;
- (e) biomanipulation to restore balanced food webs;
- (f) controlled introduction of fish or chlorella¹³ for algal control, subject to biodiversity assessments and ecological safeguards;
- (g) application of bio-dispersants or other biologically derived agents to reduce algal surface biofilms, provided that such products are accompanied by a Safety Data Sheet (SDS)¹⁴, biodegradability data (OECD 301/302), and aquatic ecotoxicity results.

5.2. The activity does not include:

- (a) ex-situ conservation actions (e.g. aquaria, botanical gardens, zoological collections);
- (b) remediation focused on hazardous pollutants (e.g. hydrocarbons, heavy metals);
- (c) catchment-level nutrient load reduction (e.g. wastewater treatment upgrades, agricultural nutrient management), which are considered essential enabling measures for reducing external nutrient pressures but are already addressed under separate Taxonomy activities.

6. Co-metrics for ecosystem recovery (SC-3, reporting only)

Projects report trends in:

- (a) dissolved oxygen (with emphasis on hypolimnetic DO during stratification);
- (b) chlorophyll-a concentrations;
- (c) cyanotoxin alerts/exceedances, where relevant to public health.

¹³ Species used must be native or demonstrably non-invasive and comply with Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 on invasive alien species and any Union-list restrictions.

¹⁴ Safety data sheets and substance/mixture compliance are governed by REACH (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006) and CLP (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008).

7. Monitoring, reporting and verification (SC-4)

7.1. MRV provides the evidence that a chosen SC-1 Outcome Pathway has been achieved, using fit-for-purpose methods, spatio-temporal replication, QA/QC, and uncertainty reporting.

Evidence Tier 1 – Direct flux (preferred). Direct measurement of methane (CH₄) flux from the water body is required for Tier 1; CO₂ and N₂O fluxes may be added where feasible. Typical methods include floating chambers; micrometeorological eddy covariance¹⁵; airborne in-situ gas analysers (e.g., drone-mounted). Capture seasonal dynamics and hot spots; report methods, calibration, boundary conditions, and uncertainty.

Evidence Tier 2: In-situ ecological proxies. Chlorophyll-a and dissolved oxygen (DO) measured in situ (multiparameter sondes, profiling) as mechanistic proxies for bloom suppression and hypoxia relief. Depth-resolved DO (especially hypolimnion); chlorophyll-a time series; co-monitor temperature/stratification. May be combined with remote sensing for spatial coverage.

Evidence Tier 3: Narrative with data trail. Documented external load reductions, bloom suppression, and oxygen recovery where Tier-1/2 are infeasible; includes an implementation plan to upgrade tiers at the next verification. Keep verifiable records (permits, plant upgrades, inflow concentrations/loads, bloom logs).

Best available technique (BAT). Where feasible, pair Tier-1 flux measurements with high-resolution remote sensing of chlorophyll-a (UAV/satellite) to improve spatial representativeness and reduce cost per unit area. Apply appropriate spatial-temporal replication and QA/QC.

7.2. CO₂-equivalent accounting (where provided). Where operators choose to report total CO₂e outcomes, they shall comply with a published MRV protocol consistent with IPCC AR6 for conversion, aggregation across working areas, treatment of CH₄ oxidation and operational emissions, and uncertainty reporting. The protocol shall be provided to the verifier and, upon request, the competent authority; public reporting may be limited to aggregated results.

8. Audit

8.1. The initial description of the water body and the management plan or equivalent instrument specified in points 2 and 3 are verified by an independent third-party certifier at the start of the remediation activity.

8.2. At the end of the duration of the management plan or equivalent instrument and at least every ten years, the achievement of the objectives set at the start of the plan and compliance with the DNSH criteria are verified. The verification includes an updated detailed description of the ecological conditions of the

¹⁵ Direct aquatic GHG flux measurements commonly include chamber techniques and micrometeorological (eddy covariance) methods; see IPCC Guidelines and 2019 Refinement context for wetlands/flooded lands.

water body as specified in point 2, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the remediation measures, including an evaluation of the effectiveness of the remediation measures, with methane (CH₄) flux reduction as the primary KPI, and, where feasible, CO₂ and N₂O; an evaluation of proxy indicators (dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a, and/or cyanotoxin); and an assessment of the MRV approach (Tier 1–3). The verification also includes an evaluation of an updated version of the management plan or equivalent instrument, and recommendations for the next plan cycle.

8.3. The verification in accordance with points 8.1 and 8.2 is carried out by either of the following:

- (a) the relevant national competent authorities;
- (b) an independent third-party certifier, at the request of national authorities or the operator of the activity.

8.4. In order to reduce costs, audits may be performed together with any water quality certification, climate certification, biodiversity certification, or other environmental audit.

8.5. The independent third-party certifier must not have any conflict of interest with the owner, the operator, or the funder, and may not be involved in the development or operation of the activity.

8.6. As a result of the verification, the certifier issues an audit report, which includes a conclusion on the effectiveness of the remediation in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, restoring nutrient and oxygen cycles, and achieving progress towards good ecological status for surface waters or good environmental status for marine waters, where applicable.

9. Guarantee of permanence

9.1. In accordance with national law, the water body where the activity takes place is covered by one of the following measures:

- (a) the area is included under a statutory framework, management plan, or restoration plan that ensures continued maintenance of nutrient and oxygen balance and prevents a return to eutrophic or anoxic conditions;
- (b) the area is designated under a freshwater, coastal, or marine use plan approved by the competent authorities, which secures the long-term implementation of remediation measures and monitoring;
- (c) the area is subject to a public or private contractual arrangement, including financing agreements, concession contracts, or municipal commitments, that ensures the continued operation of remediation infrastructure and maintenance of water quality objectives.

9.2. The operator of the activity commits that a new management plan or equivalent instrument in line with the remediation and climate mitigation objectives will be produced before the end of the previous plan's duration, to ensure continuity of measures.

9.3. Where measures involve physical installations (such as aeration systems, sediment capping, or phosphorus inactivation barriers), the operator ensures their maintenance or replacement as necessary to secure continued climate mitigation benefits and to avoid rebound of methane and nitrous oxide emissions.

9.4. Remediation projects ensure equitable public access¹⁶ to water bodies. The activity does not restrict traditional recreational and community uses such as swimming, angling, boating, or other forms of recreation, provided these do not cause harm to the restored system. Remediation improves public enjoyment and safety of water bodies by enhancing ecological health and reducing risks from eutrophication.

10. Additional minimum requirements

10.1. The offsetting of impacts from other economic activities is excluded under this activity.

10.2. The introduction of invasive alien species is prohibited. Any biomanipulation measures, such as the controlled introduction of fish or microalgae (e.g. *Chlorella*), must be subject to biodiversity assessments, ecological safeguards, and approval by the competent authority, and may only involve species that are native or demonstrably non-invasive in the specific ecological context, in line with Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014.

10.3. Any agents, additives, or dispersants used in remediation (including bio-dispersants, phosphorus inactivation products, or other biologically derived agents) must be accompanied by a Safety Data Sheet (SDS) and demonstrate compliance with EU requirements on biodegradability and aquatic toxicity.

10.4. Energy use associated with remediation installations (e.g. aeration, pumping, mixing) is monitored and reported. Operators ensure that the net greenhouse gas balance of the project remains positive, accounting for both emission reductions and operational emissions.

10.5. Remediation activities are designed and implemented in a way that respects public access and cultural uses of water bodies, in accordance with point 9.4, and ensures that societal benefits such as recreation, aesthetics, and safe water supply are preserved.

Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)

Objective	DNSH requirement
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¹⁶ This activity does not require protected-area designation and is compatible with continued recreational use, subject to safety and environmental protection rules under Union and national law.

(1) Climate change mitigation	The activity does not involve the degradation of land with high carbon stock nor the degradation of marine environments with high carbon stock.
(2) Climate change adaptation	The activity complies with the criteria set out in Appendix A to Annex I. A climate risk and vulnerability assessment is carried out, and physical or non-physical adaptation measures are implemented proportionate to the material climate risks identified.
(3) Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	The activity complies with the criteria set out in Appendix B to Annex I. It avoids deterioration in the status of water bodies and ensures efficient water use and management. Where external nutrient-load reduction measures are financed, alignment with the recast Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/3019) ¹⁷ and with river-basin or marine management plans must be demonstrated.
(4) Transition to a circular economy	N/A
(5) Pollution prevention and control	The activity complies with the criteria set out in Appendix C to Annex I. Hazardous algaecides are avoided unless risk-assessed and explicitly permitted under national law. Dredged or capped sediments are managed to prevent contaminant remobilisation and downstream pollution.
(6) Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems	The activity complies with the criteria set out in Appendix D to Annex I. An environmental impact assessment or screening is only required where mandated by EU or national law (e.g. Natura 2000 sites). No protected-area status is required for eligibility, and small water bodies are included.

Additional environmental benefits

In addition to making a substantial contribution to climate change mitigation, the remediation of eutrophic water bodies may generate further environmental benefits contributing to other environmental objectives referred to in Article 9 of Regulation (EU) 2020/852. These benefits are not part of the technical screening criteria but are recognised as positive externalities of the activity.

Objective	Additional environmental benefits
(1) Climate change mitigation	Reduction of methane (CH ₄) emissions. Optional disclosure: where total CO ₂ e outcomes are reported, results may be expressed as CO ₂ -equivalent; oxidation

¹⁷ Directive (EU) 2024/3019 (recast) strengthens requirements on nutrient removal and alignment with river-basin management planning.

	of CH ₄ to CO ₂ during oxygenation or mixing is recognised as a net benefit when transparently accounted.
(2) Climate change adaptation	Restoration of oxygen and nutrient cycles increases the resilience of aquatic ecosystems to higher temperatures, prolonged stratification, and hydrological variability. Reduced vulnerability of drinking water supplies and fisheries to climate-driven algal blooms and hypoxia.
(3) Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	Reduction in chlorophyll-a concentrations and suppression of harmful algal blooms contribute to achieving or maintaining good ecological status under Directive 2000/60/EC and good environmental status under Directive 2008/56/EC . Additional benefits include lower treatment costs, safer recreational waters, and reduced downstream nutrient transport. Overall, the activity contributes to achieving or maintaining good ecological status ¹⁸ for surface waters or good environmental status ¹⁹ for marine waters.
(4) Pollution prevention and control	Reduction of cyanotoxin occurrence and suppression of harmful algal blooms lower risks to human and animal health. Reduced reliance on hazardous algaecides or advanced chemical treatments.
(5) Transition to a circular economy	Biomass harvested during remediation can be re-used as compost, fertiliser, or bioenergy feedstock. Recovery of phosphorus supports nutrient recycling in line with the EU Circular Economy Action Plan .
(6) Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems	Recovery of fish populations, aquatic plants, and benthic invertebrates as oxygen and nutrient cycles stabilise. Strengthening of ecosystem connectivity and support for objectives under Regulation (EU) 2024/1465 on nature restoration ²⁰ .

Minimum safeguards

The activity complies with the minimum safeguards laid down in Article 18 of Regulation (EU) 2020/852. In particular:

- (a) the activity is carried out in alignment with the OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises and the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, including the principles and rights set out in the eight fundamental conventions identified in the International

¹⁸ “Good ecological status” means the status of a body of surface water as defined in Article 2, point (22), of Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.

¹⁹ “Good environmental status” means the environmental status of marine waters where these provide ecologically diverse and dynamic oceans and seas which are clean, healthy and productive, as defined in Article 3, point (5), of Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.

²⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/1465 establishes binding EU-wide restoration targets for terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems.

Labour Organisation's Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work and the International Bill of Human Rights;

(b) operators respect labour, safety, and governance standards in accordance with applicable Union and national law, including provisions on occupational health and safety, public procurement, and anti-corruption;

(c) remediation projects ensure equitable public access to water bodies. The activity does not restrict traditional recreational and community uses such as swimming, angling, boating, or other forms of recreation, provided these do not cause harm to the restored system. Instead, remediation enhances public enjoyment and safety of water bodies by improving ecological health, water quality, and aesthetics.

Additional specifications

Scope. The activity applies to all types of aquatic ecosystems affected by eutrophication, including freshwater systems (lakes, reservoirs, rivers, ponds) and marine or coastal waters prone to algal blooms and hypoxia. Artificial water bodies, such as urban ponds, irrigation reservoirs, or stormwater basins, are included where they are subject to eutrophication and generate methane or nitrous oxide emissions.

Exclusions. The activity does not cover contaminated site clean-up primarily targeting hazardous pollutants (such as hydrocarbons, heavy metals, or persistent organic pollutants), which are addressed under other Taxonomy activities. It is also not eligible as a biodiversity offset measure.

Energy use accounting. Operational energy use associated with remediation (aeration, pumping, mixing) shall be monitored and reported. Where CO₂e outcomes are reported, operational emissions are included in the CO₂e balance; otherwise, operators provide energy-use metrics and a qualitative net-benefit explanation.

Enabling measures. External nutrient-load reduction measures (for example, advanced wastewater treatment or agricultural nutrient management) are considered essential enabling actions but are classified under other Taxonomy activities. They may be financed as part of an integrated remediation plan where linkages to the water body are clearly demonstrated and alignment with Union legislation (such as Directive (EU) 2024/3019 on urban wastewater treatment and Directive 91/676/EEC on nitrates) is ensured.

Nature-based solutions. Remediation projects may refer to the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions for governance, safeguards, and monitoring of co-benefits. Such references are encouraged to support comparability and quality assurance but do not constitute eligibility thresholds under the Taxonomy.